

Data Persistence in Decentralized Social Applications: the IPFS approach

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Abstract—The Interplanetary File System (IPFS) seeks to build a decentralized, fast and efficient file system able to connect all devices worldwide. In particular, its decentralized nature makes it viable to be applied to other decentralized applications, such as Decentralized Online Social Networks. Several Blockchain Online Social Networks adopted IPFS for storing larger resources, such as videos, letting them claim to be censorship free platforms. In this paper we inspect whether IPFS is a good choice as data storage for Decentralised Social Applications, discussing its strengths and weaknesses related to our scenario. We face the problem of data storage and persistence thanks to the so-called "pinning" services implemented on top of IPFS. Additionally, we provide a set of analyses concerning physical location, protocols, and identity of the IPFS nodes discovered by our crawling node.

Index Terms—IPFS, Data Availability, Data Persistence, DOSN, BOSM

I. INTRODUCTION

Sharing content with other people and users without the use of costly third-party websites and applications has been an issue for multiple years. One of the main problems of distributed systems, like P2P networks, is the data availability [1]. Indeed, decentralized applications suffer from this issue and they require to exploit external solutions, such as distributed storage or file system to improve the availability of data. One of the most well-known application is IPFS [2]. IPFS is a distributed file system, used as a distributed data storage service, and for sharing content in a censorship-resistant manner, frequently used by decentralized applications, mainly based on blockchain technology. Distributed file systems are used to allow multiple users to access and store files on a shared file system over networks. Nowadays, distributed file systems, like IPFS, allow users to share content through their own devices when they are online. Users can share their content with anyone who has the hash, the only requirement is that at least one node has the content that they are trying to share. The need to be online to share data, it is a big limitation.

Among the several decentralized applications, Decentralized Online Social Media (DOSNs) [3] and Blockchain Online Social Media (BOSMs) [4] represents an interesting scenario due to the huge amount of social data (images, video, etc.). As concerns DOSNs, several solutions have been proposed to store social data among peers [5]–[7] or by exploiting external services [8], [9]. Instead, as concerns BOSMs, they are principally based on external storages due to the blockchain which

can not be used to store huge amount of information. Among BOSMs, Peepeth¹, Akasha², and DTube³, currently use IPFS.

In this paper, we analyse the problem of data persistence in decentralized applications, by using the Decentralized Social Media as a case of study. The goal is to evaluate how IPFS can be used in these systems, and how the current services offered by IPFS can be useful to overcome the data availability issue. We start our work by analysing the pinning services built on top of IPFS. Considering that data is hosted by an open set of peers, the privacy of social data becomes again the main requirement to develop a decentralized social application. For this reason, we analyse more in details the characteristics of IPFS, and which privacy solutions can be used in combination with the pinning services. Finally, we explore the IPFS P2P network to gain insights about the identity of the nodes in the network and understand whether IPFS is a good candidate to be used as data storage in our reference scenario of decentralised social media.

II. WHAT IS IPFS?

IPFS is a P2P file system to store and share data. Content added to IPFS receives a unique hash corresponding to the contents of the resource (i.e. files in a folder or contents of a file). The hash is unique and is totally different even if there is only a difference of one single character. IPFS can use the content of the file to locate its address, instead of using a domain name, as HTTP does. The name of the data is immutable. The references between data items and their respective providers are stored in a Kademlia-based DHT. The DHT is used for routing, which means to announce newly added data to the network, and help to locate data that is requested by any node. Small values (about 1KB) are stored directly on the DHT. For values larger, the DHT stores references, which are the NodeIds of peers who can serve the block.

There are three fundamental principles to understanding IPFS⁴:

- Unique identification via content addressing;
- Content linking via Directed Acyclic Graphs (DAGs);
- Content discovery via Distributed Hash Tables (DHTs).

¹<https://peepeth.com/>

²<https://akasha.world/>

³<https://d.tube/>

⁴<https://docs.ipfs.io/>

Figure 1 shows the IPFS stack. There are three layers: the first one is for using the data, the second for defining the data, and the last one is for moving the data.

Fig. 1. Stack IPFS

For distributing files and data, IPFS uses the BitSwap protocol, similar to the BitTorrent protocol. BitSwap is a message-based protocol where all messages contain want-lists or blocks. Indeed, it acquires blocks requested by the client having a “wantList”, and it sends blocks to peers that have a “haveList” [2]. Blocks are binary structures of data that contain a certain amount of the files information. When peers exchange blocks they keep track of the amount of data they share and the amount of data they receive in the BitSwap Ledger.

Another important structure is the Merkle Directed Acyclic Graph (Merkel DAG), a tree that is used to several purposes⁵:

- Verify the unique hash of each object;
- Verify that transferred data are not tampered or corrupted;
- Check if two objects have the same content. In that specific case, the two objects are considered equal and only stored once.

Merkel DAGs are similar to Merkle trees, but there are no balance requirements and every node can carry a payload.

III. IPFS AND DECENTRALIZED SOCIAL APPLICATIONS

Among the several decentralized applications which use IPFS, we decide to focus on social applications, as a case study. Current Blockchain-based Social Media are widely based on IPFS due to the need for a repository where to store all the social data (videos, images, etc..) shared among users. Blockchain can not be used to store this kind of data.

We highlight two requirements that need to be faced to apply IPFS to decentralized social systems:

- Privacy issues and control over personal data. User data needs to be stored and accessible only from who has permission to access.

- Data Availability issue. Data should be persistent and permanent in the network to overcome the data availability issue.

Concerning the first requirement, all files in IPFS are available to the public, which is not a desirable feature for most social applications, and anyone who has the hash can access the data because it is not possible to define access policies. As expressed in [10], privacy is an important issue, and a decentralized social application should give to the user the possibility to store private data, which can only be accessed by certain entities. A possible solution proposed by IPFS is the possibility to build a private network which can be accessed only from specific authorized users. Furthermore, IPFS gateways are helpful to retrieve content on the IPFS network without running their own IPFS node, and they are a useful tool for users looking to hide their identity while requesting content on the IPFS network.

The main problem regarding availability and reliability in common-used applications and services is that if they happen to have downtime, and the resource might not be available. There are also problems regarding reliability, due to man-in-the-middle attacks or other similar attacks. Both these aspects are managed, in IPFS, by using multiple nodes, replication of resources, and hashing of content. In the rest of the paper, we will discuss in detail the issue concerning the persistence of data.

IV. PERSISTENCE, PERMANENCE, AND PINNING

IPFS nodes store data like in a cache, which means that data will be not available in the future. For this reason, IPFS provides the “Pinning” service. Thanks to this kind of service nodes can pin their data as important and the data will be not removed from the network. The pinning service is useful when the node is a phone or a tablet, that could have intermittent connectivity to the network. Indeed, in the case of private networks, data replication can be achieved using specifically designed protocols and the resources of the nodes in the network. However, it may be not enough to use only the nodes that are in that network, especially in the case of mobile networks or other decentralised networks affected by high churn rates. Pinning services implemented on top of IPFS can come in handy because these services often run long-lived host nodes on a cloud service provider to store the data. As concerns privacy, users must trust in pinning services because they must either rely on other peers to voluntarily/altruistically pin their data. Pinning services are not free, and when a user pins a certain amount of data on an IPFS pinning service, he/she will pay monthly fees associated with that data.

IPFS pinning service improves the speed of retrieving data. There are two major advantages to relying on an IPFS pinning service for speed. First, IPFS pinning services are often highly connected to other nodes in the IPFS network. Second, IPFS can leverage parallelization while retrieving data.

⁵<https://docs.ipfs.io/>

Service	Hash Pinning	Private Network	Encrypted	Gateway
Pinata	✓	✓	✓	✓
Temporal	✓	✓	✓	✓
Eternum	✓	-	-	✓

TABLE I
PINNING SERVICES ON IPFS

Table I shows the functionalities of three famous pinning services provided directly on IPFS: Pinata⁶, Temporal⁷, and Eternum⁸. We analyse the three services by comparing four different functionalities. We highlight the possibility to pin the hash, which is a common characteristics of all the three services; the possibility to set a private network and uses the services over a private network, which is provided only by Pinata and Temporal; the encryption of data, which is provided by Pinata and Temporal, and finally the possibility to use the service through a gateway, which is common to all the services. The analyses shows that Pinata and Temporal represent two more complete services compared to Eternum, which is simple, easy to use, but with less functionalities. All the three services are based on paid plans based on the amount of data pinned.

V. ANALYSIS OF IPFS NODES

In this Section, we will analyse the location and the identity of the IPFS nodes. Thanks to these analyses, we aim to shed light concerning which are the most common pinning services, whether they are hosted on cloud services, and the physical location of these nodes. In particular, the physical location of the pinning services is crucial in case data residency and data localisation laws must be enforced. We start our preliminary analysis by monitoring the IPFS network by setting up an IPFS node and a script to log the known nodes at a fixed time rate (i.e. once every 5 minutes). The node logged the connected peers for two days, from Wednesday the 23rd of September 2020 17:25 to Friday the 25th of September 2020 17:25.

In Figure 2 we show the most common country of the peers with which our node came in contact with. The countries are identified by their ISO_3166-1_alpha-2 codes, which is an internationally recognised naming standard. Most of the peers are from the United States of America (country code US), with almost than 2,700 peers. Other important countries are China (country code CN) with 1,300 peers, and Hong Kong (country code HK) with 762 peers, followed by Taiwan. It is interesting to see that among to top recurring countries, a fair number of them are the ones that have censorship troubles. For such countries, IPFS can help people reach content otherwise unreachable or obfuscated within the country. The country code ZZ is a special code which is used when it was not possible to detect the real country. In our case LACNINC, the Regional Internet Registry for Latin America and Caribbeans, did not correctly process most of our requests and returned ZZ

Fig. 2. Most common countries.

Fig. 3. Most common network names.

as country code. The total number of country codes detected is 95; most European countries and many Asian countries appear in the list.

We additionally inspected the network name of each IP address gathered, shown in Figure 3. The plot shows that the vast majority of the network names belong to companies that offer cloud services. The most common is Tencent, which is a Chinese company which focuses on entertainment (video games in particular) and internet services. Other recurring network names are connected to DigitalOcean, which is a cloud infrastructure provider based in the USA. The main reason why IP addresses related to cloud infrastructures appear is linked to the fact that people can deploy an IPFS node on cloud infrastructures and then host their websites using IPFS. In the specific case of Tencent, we know that many Blockchain Online Social Media [4], such as the ones based on Tron and Steem [11], are based in China and use IPFS to store some contents, such as videos. Other relevant network names include Netvigator and HGC Global, which are ISP in Hong Kong, meaning that most users from Hong Kong are private users, not cloud providers. In total, we came across 1,365 network names.

Lastly, we use our IPFS node to study the transport protocols used and the physical location of the peers through time. Figure 4 shows the transport protocols used by the IPFS nodes. The TCP protocol is largely preferred by the nodes, thanks to it properties of reliability and error-checked delivery

⁶<https://pinata.cloud/>

⁷<https://temporal.cloud/>

⁸<https://www.eternum.io/>

Fig. 4. Most common protocols used by the nodes during the observation period.

Fig. 5. Country of the nodes during the observation period.

of messages. However, it must be noted that a non-negligible number of nodes uses QUIC [12], an enhanced version of UDP, because of the reduced latency in the communications. The results concerning the location of IPFS nodes are shown in Figure 5. We decided to show USA and China (respectively red and green lines) separately because they were the two most common countries according to the preliminary analyses, while we grouped all the European countries (blue line) and all the other countries (yellow line). The USA is by far the most popular origin country of the connected peers, and additionally, we observe that China is not as popular as in the general statistics (see Figure 2). This plot shows that USA nodes are very stable and that our node was able to connect to them repeatedly, while the same was not possible for the Chinese nodes. One possible cause of this effect is connected to a different usage that nodes originating from the two countries make of the IPFS network, as we discussed earlier in this Section.

In another similar study [13] the crawling node was able to connect to a more heterogeneous population of nodes, covering a broader area. On the other hand, authors focus on a different goal more related to the P2P network, and they do not study in much detail the identity of the nodes.

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORKS

The implementation of Decentralized Social Applications has several requirements, such as privacy, scalability, but in particular the data availability, which is not guaranteed by centralized servers. Nowadays, IPFS is widely used as a support for decentralized applications, in particular blockchain-based. In this paper, we highlighted the requirements of DOSNs

and BOSMs applications. We highlighted the limitation in using IPFS concerning privacy and the possible solutions that could be used in that specific scenario. Furthermore, we explained which methods could be used in order to improve the persistence of data, and methods to preserving privacy on IPFS, like private IPFS networks, content encryption, and gateway utilization. We provided a preliminary analysis of the IPFS network. The analyses showed that cloud infrastructure services are the most common IPFS nodes, which are used for pinning services, but also for the gateway service, and others. We showed that most of them reside in the USA. As future work, we plan to go more in-depth concerning the structure of the IPFS network. Indeed, we are currently monitoring them to extend our analysis. Additionally, we plan to investigate more in detail the current pinning services by analysing external services such as Filecoin, and we plan to develop automatic strategies for data pinning, such that this technique can seamlessly be applied to Decentralized Social Applications.

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REFERENCES

- [1] B. Guidi, M. Conti, A. Passarella, and L. Ricci, "Managing social contents in decentralized online social networks: A survey," *Online Social Networks and Media*, vol. 7, pp. 12–29, 2018.
- [2] J. Benet, "Ipfs-content addressed, versioned, p2p file system," *arXiv preprint arXiv:1407.3561*, 2014.
- [3] A. Datta, S. Buchegger, L.-H. Vu, T. Strufe, and K. Rzadca, "Decentralized online social networks," in *Handbook of Social Network Technologies and Applications*, 2010, pp. 349–378.
- [4] B. Guidi, "When blockchain meets online social networks," *Pervasive and Mobile Computing*, vol. 62, p. 101131, 2020.
- [5] R. Narendula, A. Papaioannou, and K. Aberer, "A Decentralized Online Social Network with Efficient User-Driven Replication," in *IEEE International conference on Social Computing (SocialCom 2012)*, 2012.
- [6] B. Guidi, T. Amft, A. De Salve, K. Graffi, and L. Ricci, "Didusonet: A p2p architecture for distributed dunbar-based social networks," *Peer-to-Peer Networking and Applications*, vol. 9, no. 6, pp. 1177–1194, 2016.
- [7] L. A. Cuttillo, R. Molva, and T. Strufe, "Safebook: A privacy-preserving online social network leveraging on real-life trust," *Comm. Mag.*, vol. 47, no. 12, pp. 94–101, Dec. 2009.
- [8] A. Shakimov, H. Lim, R. Cáceres, L. P. Cox, K. Li, D. Liu, and A. Varshavsky, "Vis-a-vis: Privacy-preserving online social networking via virtual individual servers," in *COMSNETS*, 2011, pp. 1–10.
- [9] R. Sharma and A. Datta, "Supernova: Super-peers based architecture for decentralized online social networks," in *COMSNETS*, 2012, pp. 1–10.
- [10] A. De Salve, P. Mori, and L. Ricci, "A survey on privacy in decentralized online social networks," *Computer Science Review*, vol. 27, pp. 154–176, 2018.
- [11] K. Kapanova, B. Guidi, A. Michienzi, and K. Koidl, "Evaluating posts on the steemit blockchain: Analysis on topics based on textual cues," in *Proceedings of the 6th EAI International Conference on Smart Objects and Technologies for Social Good*, 2020, pp. 163–168.
- [12] A. Langley, A. Riddoch, A. Wilk, A. Vicente, C. Krasic, D. Zhang, F. Yang, F. Kouranov, I. Swett, J. Iyengar *et al.*, "The quic transport protocol: Design and internet-scale deployment," in *Proceedings of the Conference of the ACM Special Interest Group on Data Communication*, 2017, pp. 183–196.
- [13] S. Henningsen, M. Florian, S. Rust, and B. Scheuermann, "Mapping the interplanetary filesystem," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2002.07747*, 2020.